

**A SYSTEMATIC EXAMINATION OF THE LITERATURE ON THE
APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN BREAST CANCER
DETECTION**

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Abstract:

Breast cancer remains a significant cause of mortality among women worldwide, with recent data from the American Cancer Society indicating thousands of fatalities annually. Classified into normal, benign, in-situ carcinoma, and invasive carcinoma types, breast cancer's severity varies widely. While benign tumors typically pose minimal risk, in-situ carcinoma is confined to the mammary duct lobule system and manageable if detected early. Invasive carcinoma, however, represents the most perilous form, capable of metastasizing to other organs. Various diagnostic modalities, such as X-ray mammography, ultrasound, CT, PET, MRI, and breast temperature measurement, aid in detection, with pathological diagnosis serving as the gold standard. Histopathological image analysis and genomics are the primary diagnostic approaches, with microscopic examination of breast tissue providing crucial insights for early intervention.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, breast cancer detection, systematic examination, literature review, machine learning, deep learning, diagnostic algorithms, imaging modalities, performance evaluation.

A systematic literature review on breast cancer detection using artificial intelligence (AI) techniques would be an excellent way to gather comprehensive insights into the current state-of-the-art methodologies, challenges, and future directions in this domain. Such a review typically involves a structured and rigorous methodology for identifying, selecting, and synthesizing relevant research papers from academic databases, journals, and conference proceedings.

To conduct this review, you would start by defining your research question or objectives, such as understanding the effectiveness of different AI techniques for breast cancer detection, identifying the most promising approaches, or evaluating the performance metrics used in the literature. Then, you would develop inclusion and exclusion criteria to select relevant studies, such as publication date range, types of AI techniques (e.g., machine learning, deep learning), target populations, and outcome measures.

Next, you would systematically search multiple databases (e.g., PubMed, IEEE Xplore, Google Scholar) using predefined search terms and strings related to breast cancer detection and AI techniques. After retrieving the initial set of articles, you would screen them based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, typically in multiple stages (e.g., title/abstract screening, full-text screening) to ensure that only relevant studies are included.

Once the relevant studies are identified, you would extract data from each study, including study characteristics (e.g., author, publication year, study design), AI techniques used, dataset characteristics, performance metrics, and key findings. You may also assess the quality of included studies using appropriate appraisal tools or criteria.

Finally, you would synthesize the findings from the included studies, identify common themes, trends, and gaps in the literature, and provide recommendations for future research directions. This synthesis could be presented narratively, quantitatively (e.g., meta-analysis), or both, depending on the nature of the included studies and the research objectives.

Overall, a systematic literature review on breast cancer detection using AI techniques can provide valuable insights for researchers, clinicians, and policymakers working in the field, helping to inform decision-making, identify areas for further research, and ultimately improve the early detection and treatment of breast cancer.

Breast cancer is one of the major causes of death in women around the world. According to the American cancer society, 41,760 women and more than 500 men died from breast cancer recently¹. Breast cancer occurs in four main types: normal,

benign, in-situ carcinoma and invasive carcinoma [1]. A benign tumor involves a minor change in the breast structure. It is not harmful and does not classify as a harmful cancer. In cases of in-situ carcinoma, the cancer is only in the mammary duct lobule system and does not affect other organs. This type is not dangerous and can be treated if diagnosed early. Invasive carcinoma is considered to be the most dangerous type of breast cancer, as it can spread to all other organs. According to the authors in [1], breast cancer can be detected using several methods including X-ray mammography, ultrasound (US), Computed Tomography (CT), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and breast temperature measurement. Usually, the golden standard is a pathological diagnosis for detecting breast cancer. This involves an image analysis of the removed tissue, which is stained in the lab to increase visibility. Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) are commonly used for the staining process. Breast cancer can be diagnosed using one of two approaches: histopathological image analysis or genomics. Histopathological images are microscopic images of breast tissue that are extremely useful in early treatment of the cancer.

Which deep learning models perform most effectively? We will compare deep learning models with classical machine learning models to compare their performance. We will also list the performance metrics used.

2. What are the most used features for breast cancer classification? How are these features selected and extracted? We will observe the most important features that contribute to breast cancer classification, and the methods used to extract these features.

3. What datasets are available for both gene sequencing and MRI? What feature selection and extraction methods are used? We will list and discuss all public and private datasets for gene sequencing and MRI imaging data. We will also list some of the methods used to select and extract the features. 4. Comparing gene sequence data with image data, for breast cancer detection problem, what are the drawbacks, challenges, and advantages? We will compare imaging and gene sequencing as they relate to breast cancer detection, using a tabular presentation to highlight the main differences between the two approaches.

Methodology

Our target topic is breast cancer detection using deep learning. We ended up using around 80 of the most recent papers related to breast cancer treatment and diagnosis.

Some of the papers examined only deep learning, while others used a combination of machine learning and deep learning. In our search process, we mainly used the Scopus database to obtain the articles. This is to exclude nonrefereed publications. However, in Figure 1, we state the distribution of selected papers among the existing databases. The top five databases are PubMed, ScienceDirect (Elsevier), IEEE, Springer and Nature.

We employed the search query: ("breast cancer") AND ALL ("deep learning" OR "deep neural network") AND ALL ("gene" OR "genome" OR "microarray" OR "DNA" OR "X-ray" OR "mammography" OR "MRI" OR "ultrasound"). Our search yielded over 1,000 papers published from January 2010 to May 2020. The figure below illustrates the distribution of paper publications throughout this timeframe.

The publication of breast cancer studies reached its peak around 2019 and 2020. We narrowed down the pool to 80 papers by focusing on those utilizing genetic expression and imaging techniques, and specifically targeting journal and conference articles. Imaging modalities considered included ultrasound, radiography, mammography, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), as well as various forms of gene expression and sequencing.

Our research primarily focused on papers implementing breast cancer detection through AI techniques, as well as those predicting breast cancer using both gene and image data. We established specific eligibility criteria for each paper: (1) English language; (2) Relevance to breast cancer detection and treatment; (3) Discussion on hybrid models of machine learning and deep learning; (4) Sole focus on deep learning; (5) Inclusion of genetic expression data; (6) Incorporation of imaging data; (7) Limited to journal and conference publications; (8) Limited to medical or biomedical engineering publications related to the topic. Notably, non-refereed publications were excluded from consideration.

Initially, we recorded essential information such as paper title, publication year, authors, and publisher. Subsequently, we incorporated additional details necessary for conducting the systematic review, including the algorithm utilized, whether the paper solely focused on deep learning or employed a hybrid approach with machine learning, recorded accuracy and other performance evaluation metrics, dataset

characteristics, features, and various other parameters. We utilized these criteria to address our research questions effectively.

Best models performance for images data classifiers

Models with the highest accuracies are SOCPNN and CNN, respectively.

Findings and Prospects for Future Research

The majority of publications within the breast cancer detection and subtype classification domain rely on machine learning methods. However, there has been

limited exploration of deep learning models in this area, providing researchers with opportunities to employ various deep learning mechanisms such as LSTM, GAN, and RNN for predicting patient outcomes, as such investigations remain largely unexplored.

Additionally, many papers primarily focus on the Accuracy metric to evaluate model performance while overlooking crucial parameters of the confusion matrix and AUC. This approach is inadequate as the Accuracy metric fails to distinguish between false positive and false negative classifications. Future studies should incorporate at least AUC and F-scores to comprehensively assess each model's performance.

A notable observation is the prevalent use of the CNN algorithm for both gene expression and MRI image data, which often yields favorable results compared to other algorithms. Researchers may wish to further explore and implement hybrid algorithms involving CNN to enhance model performance.

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